

EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF WORK-FAMILY CONFLICT AND WORK-LIFE BALANCE ON PERFORMANCE IN THE MANUFACTURING INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>This study examines the relationships between work-family conflict and work-life balance with job satisfaction and employee performance, highlighting the mediating role of job satisfaction. The population of this study was 861 production department employees. Data analysis uses Descriptive Statistical Analysis and Inferential Analysis using the SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) method using Smarts PLS 3.0. The results indicate that work-family conflict significantly and negatively impacts both job satisfaction and employee performance. The stronger the work-family conflict, the lower the job satisfaction, and hence, the lower the performance. It also identifies emotional exhaustion, psychological stress, and role imbalance as negative outcomes of work-family conflict for male and female employees. On the other hand, work-life balance influences the employees' job satisfaction and performance positively. Whenever employees are able to balance between their work and personal life, they tend to portray a high level of job satisfaction and improvement in their performances. The results further denote that job satisfaction mediates in the relationship of work-family conflict and work-life balance with employee performance, but the direct influences of work-family conflict and work-life balance on performance are stronger than the indirect effects via job satisfaction. The study concludes that work-family conflict must be confronted head-on, and life-work balance policies must be implemented to realize high levels of job satisfaction and performance. These facts have useful implications for organizational management in the pursuit of a supportive and productive work environment.</p>	<p>Work-family conflict, Work-life balance, Job satisfaction, Job performance</p>

I. INTRODUCTION

Research on work-family conflict and work-life balance highlights the relationship between various factors and their impact on numerous aspects of employee well-being. Studies show that work-family conflict can lead to poor judgment from employees (Ziedelis et al., 2023). For example, female employees who face challenges in balancing work and family responsibilities (Weale et al., 2023). Apart from that, a less conducive work climate in the organization can make work-family conflicts worse. This research is aimed at examining the influence of

work-family conflict and work-life balance on job satisfaction and its implications for employee performance. This research was carried out in the manufacturing industry, which applies a work shift system until night. Management policy does not permit employees who want to change work shifts. As a result, employees are less able to divide their roles between their families and work, and as a result, annual production targets cannot be achieved (Kosseck & Kelliher, 2022). This study examines the relationships between workers and management through the perspective of social exchange theory. According to this concept, when one party helps another, the recipient usually returns the favor by helping the previous party and giving them favorable treatment (Qian & Kan, 2024). Social Exchange Theory is frequently applied in the context of organizational behavior to explain how mutual exchanges serve to build and maintain relationships between employers and employees (Susanto et al., 2022).

In previous studies, the research population consisted of company employees in general, whereas in this study, it was only limited to production employees who belonged to the millennial generation. The millennial generation places value on the balance between work and personal life. In addition to seeking a high pay, they also want an environment at work that encourages them to combine their personal and professional lives (Drewery et al., 2023; Hidayat & Aulia, 2023). According to the National Development Planning Agency, the workforce in Indonesia is dominated by the Millennial generation (Elian, 2020). Totaling 63 million individuals, which accounts for approximately 24% of the country's total population. Millennials encompass both women and men born between 1984 and 1999, ranging in age from 21 to 36 years old. There is much research on job performance and satisfaction, but specifically, the millennial generation is still rarely researched. Studies have identified several adverse outcomes associated with work-family conflict, including symptoms of strain, fatigue, and disengagement from work, all of which impact their productivity (Huo & Jiang, 2023). Work-family conflict has a significant effect on employee performance, according to empirical study (Fan et al., 2024; Obrenovic et al., 2020). However, other empirical research shows that the influence of these two variables is not substantial (Ribeiro et al., 2023). So further research is needed.

Job performance and satisfaction have an essential role for organizations, especially in a competitive business environment (Memon et al., 2023). Job satisfaction is a collection of positive feelings of employees towards their work, and this shows the success of the organization. Job satisfaction has a varied influence on multiple facets of the organization (Arshad et al., 2023; Khahro, 2016). Job satisfaction is more straightforward to realize if a work-life balance exists (Priya et al., 2023). In academic research, work-life balance and work-family conflict are frequently studied due to their interconnected nature. Balance is achieved when there is no conflict between the roles individuals play at home and at work, ensuring harmony between employees' professional and personal lives (Qiu & Dauth, 2022). Work-life balance positively impacts a person's achievements, including employee performance. Likewise, increasing job satisfaction has an impact on employee performance. Enhanced job satisfaction boosts employee capability, potentially leading to improved work performance when effectively managed (Susanto et al., 2022). Unsupportive production policies can create an imbalance between employees and employees' personal lives, which can affect job satisfaction and employee performance. Therefore, research questions this research: How are the influence of work-family conflict and work-life balance on job satisfaction and performance of millennial generation production employees?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Social exchange Theory

Social Exchange Theory is a framework in sociology and social psychology that considers interactions between individuals from the perspective of anticipated costs and benefits (Qian & Kan, 2024). According to this theory, individuals tend to act in accordance with their self-interest, taking into account what they believe will provide the best results for them (Emerson, 2008). This theory emphasizes that individuals enter social relationships because they expect rewards that exceed the costs they incur. These rewards can take the form of emotional satisfaction, social support, practical help, or other resources. However, individuals also consider the costs associated with maintaining the relationship, such as time, energy, or personal sacrifice (Ahmad et al., 2022; Blau, 2017).

Relationship between Work-Family Conflict, Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance

Work-family conflict (WFC) arises from conflicts between work and family responsibilities, such as time, access, and performance. Every worker works to provide financial support to the family, but if they cannot offer personal time for the family, then Work-Family Conflict can occur. Work-family conflict also affects performance and productivity (Priya et al., 2023). Individuals who face Work-Family Conflict need to rearrange their jobs or work schedules so that their work is more satisfying (Handelzalts et al., 2024). To achieve competitiveness, individuals must maintain a balance between work and family time because the conflict between work and family responsibilities can adversely affect performance (Zhang et al., 2020).

Work-family conflict is associated with increased work fatigue and work stress as well as decreased health, organizational commitment and employee performance (Tran, 2023). Work-family conflict occurs when commitments and interests at work interfere with family life, such as irregular or inflexible working hours, excessive workload, stress, interpersonal conflict at work, and an unsupportive boss or organization (Laß & Wooden, 2022; Weale et al., 2023). The destructive consequences of workfamily conflict, such as depression, work fatigue, employee turnover, job dissatisfaction and marital discord, were found to intensify as conflicts between work and family responsibilities increased among employees (Yadav & Sharma, 2023).

Research has identified several adverse outcomes associated with work-family conflict, including symptoms of stress, fatigue, and employee disengagement, all of which impact employee performance (Huo & Jiang, 2023). The results reveal that work-family conflict has a negative effect on job satisfaction. In addition, the research results show that work-family conflict acts as a relevant predictor of job satisfaction. Several studies indicate a negative correlation between work-family conflicts and job satisfaction. As previously discussed, reducing work-family conflicts will improve employee attitudes and job satisfaction. Bad consequences such as depression, work fatigue, were found to increase due to excessive work-family conflict (Yadav & Sharma, 2023). Work-family conflict has a significant and negative effect on job satisfaction (Zhao et al., 2023). Employee-family conflict has been shown to have a detrimental effect on work productivity (Batur & Nart, 2014). Family-employee issues has been found to significantly and negatively impact performance (Warokka & Febrilia, 2014). Based on this description, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Work-family conflict affects job satisfaction

H2: Work-family conflict affects employee performance

Relationship between Work-Life Balance, Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance

Work-life balance (WLB) is form of balance as a professional employee with family responsibilities and personal activities. This involves effectively managing and integrating work and non-work domains to reduce conflict and improve well-being. Individuals have a good work balance, fulfil the demands of their roles as employees and

family members, and reduce conflict and compatibility (Kerdpitak & Jermstittiparsert, 2020; Priya et al., 2023). It signifies how individuals meet or should meet their professional and personal responsibilities to prevent overlapping situations (Susanto et al., 2022). Regardless of size, organizations must ensure that employees have sufficient time to fulfil their family and work commitments (Bouwmeester et al., 2020). Research shows that work-life balance is essential for improving employee performance because it affects productivity and job satisfaction (Gragnano et al., 2020).

Organizations that pay attention to this balance can improve employee performance, thereby benefiting the company as a valuable asset. (Susanto et al., 2022; Preena & Preena, 2021). Work-life balance has a positive impact on work performance because household harmony and work-life balance increase job satisfaction. Activities in the family and work environment provide individuals with autonomy and self-confidence, thereby influencing their emotional responses to their work. This balance has a positive impact on work-life balance and job performance (Fiernaningsih et al., 2019; Uresha, 2020; Qiu & Dauth, 2022; Thi et al., 2022). Based on this, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H3: Work-life balance influence on job satisfaction

H4: Work-life balance influence on employee performance

Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance

Job satisfaction reflects an individual's emotional response to their job (Winton, 2023). Job satisfaction is an essential factor that has an impact on a person's success as an employee and is very beneficial for the company. Therefore, employee job satisfaction is an essential driving force for organizations (Priya et al., 2023). High job satisfaction can significantly benefit employees by boosting their self-confidence and reinforcing their professional identity. When employees feel satisfied with their job, they are more likely to perform their duties diligently and proactively seek ways to improve. This positive mindset also fosters better relationships with coworkers, as content employees tend to communicate and collaborate more effectively. Furthermore, high job satisfaction can alleviate mental stress, leading to a healthier work environment (Fleury & Grenier, 2018). Job satisfaction will affect employee performance. There is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance because employees who are satisfied and can enjoy their work will tend to perform better in carrying out their roles based on social exchange theory (Cho et al., 2023). Increased job satisfaction leads to improved work performance (Hartika et al., 2023). Employees who have high job satisfaction are found to have higher performance scores as well. That shows that individuals who are satisfied with their employees will work better in carrying out their tasks. Employees who are satisfied and enjoy their work will tend to perform better in carrying out their roles based on social exchange theory (Cho et al., 2023).

Job satisfaction can predict employee performance positively (Hartika et al., 2023). Increasing employee job satisfaction influences employee performance (Berhanu, 2023; Lu et al., 2023; Maheshwari, 2022). Research demonstrates that employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to be more productive, thus benefiting their employers. When employees find satisfaction in their jobs, they perceive their work as meaningful. As they gain confidence in their ability to complete work-related tasks (Memon et al., 2023). Employee performance is a form of employee expertise in carrying out their duties in a way that supports the organization in achieving its goals (Moonsri, 2018). In terms of numerous employee-related behaviors and outcomes, it can also be described as an individual's job productivity relative to that of their colleagues (Aeknarajindawat & Jermstittiparsert, 2020). "Individual performance" refers to personal achievements and the extent to which organizational tasks are successfully completed. Employee performance encompasses both the quality and quantity of work delivered as

employees fulfill tasks assigned by their supervisors or leaders, based on their organizational roles. This concept includes the effectiveness with which employees meet their duties, contribute to organizational objectives, and adhere to standards set by their superiors, reflecting their overall efficiency and productivity (Memon et al., 2023). Based on this, the following hypothesis is formulated: H5: Job Satisfaction Influences Employee Performance

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses a quantitative paradigm. The type of research used is explanatory research to test the influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. Exogenous variables consist of work-family conflict and work-life balance. The endogenous variable is employee performance. The intervening variable is job satisfaction. The operationalization of this research variable is as follows: work-family conflict is a form of conflict between roles that originates from conflicting work and family spheres (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985). Work-family conflict indicators are time-based conflict, Strain-based Conflict, and behaviour-based Conflict (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985). Work-family conflict was assessed using five Likert scales, namely (1) strongly disagree, (2) disagree, (3) neutral, (4) agree, and (5) strongly agree. Work-life balance is the ability to balance responsibilities at work and personal life responsibilities to improve well-being (Priya et al., 2023). Indicators of work-life balance: Time Balance, Involvement Balance, and Satisfaction Balance (Greenhaus & Collins, 2003). The assessment of Work-Life Balance utilized a five-point Likert scale, ranging from (1) completely disagree, (2) disagree, (3) neutral, (4) agree, and (5) completely agree. Job satisfaction is a happy emotional state caused by the results of an individual's job assessment or work experience (Luthans, 2011). Indicators of job satisfaction are satisfaction with work, payment, and promotion of employees, supervisors and co-workers (Luthans, 2011). Five Likert scales: (1) completely disagree, (2) disagree, (3) neutral, (4) agree, and (5) completely agree, were used to measure satisfaction among workers. Employee performance is the value of a series of employee behaviours that contribute, either positively or negatively, to the achievement of organizational goals (Moonsri, 2018). Employee performance indicators are quality of work, quantity of work, responsibility, cooperation, initiative, and compliance with procedures (Colcuitt et al., 2017). Five Likert scales are used to measure employee performance: (1) fully disagree, (2) disagree, (3) neutral, (4) agree, and (5) completely agree.

The respondents of this research are PT employees. Penca Bersoedaraan Sedjati, who works in the production department, belongs to the millennial generation (born between 1984 and 1999 with an age range of 21 to 36 years), totaling 861 people. Data collection was carried out using a questionnaire. This research uses inferential statistics processed through the Smarts PLS

(Partial Least Square) application. The PLS analysis technique is carried out in three stages, namely, out an outer model test (measurement model), namely testing the validity and reliability of the construct of each indicator. The second stage is to carry out an inner model (structural model) test, which is carried out to ensure that the structural model that is built is precise and accurate. The third stage is hypothesis testing.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
<input type="checkbox"/> Male	370	43 %

<input type="checkbox"/> Female	491	57 %
Marital		
<input type="checkbox"/> Not married	121	14 %
<input type="checkbox"/> Married	740	86 %
Tenure of employees		
<input type="checkbox"/> < 1 year	17	2%
<input type="checkbox"/> 15 years	655	76%
<input type="checkbox"/> >5 – 10 years	189	22%
Education		
<input type="checkbox"/> Senior high school	662	77%
<input type="checkbox"/> Diploma	164	19 %
<input type="checkbox"/> Bachelor	35	4%
Total	861	100%

Based on Table 1, most respondents were female (57%), married (86%), had worked for 1-5 years (76%), and had a senior high school education (77%).

Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis research can be answered by testing the significance of the influence between constructs by looking at the t-statistic value. Path coefficient values can be obtained through the PLS Bootstrapping model. Results of hypothesis testing is carried out by looking at Table 2 .

Table 2. Results of Hypothesis Testing

	Hypothesis	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics	p Values	Description
H1	Work-family Conflict (X1) -> Job Satisfaction (Z)	-0.558	5,694	0,000	accepted
H2	Work-family Conflict (X1) -> Employee Performance (Y)	-0.371	4,368	0,000	accepted
H3	Work-life Balance(X2) -> Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.309	2,949	0.003	accepted
H4	Work-life Balance(X2) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.224	2,154	0.032	accepted
H5	Job Satisfaction (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.387	4,839	0,000	accepted
H6	Work-family Conflict(X1) -> Job Satisfaction (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	-0.216	3,576	0,000	accepted

H7	Work-life Balance(X2) -> Job Satisfaction (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.120	2,552	0.011	accepted
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Source: Primary data processed in 2023

1. Effect of Work-Family Conflict (X1) on Job Satisfaction (Z)

Hypothesis testing shows that the work-family conflict variable has a significant effect on Job Satisfaction because the t-statistic value is $5.694 > t\text{-table } 1.65$ and the p-value is $0.000 < 0.05$. Furthermore, the path coefficient value is -0.558 (negative), which means that the influence of the work-family conflict variable on Job Satisfaction is in the opposite direction or inversely proportional. The higher the work-family conflict, the lower the level of job satisfaction, and vice versa. Therefore, it can be concluded that work-family conflict (X1) significantly influences Job Satisfaction (Z).

2. Effect of Work-Family Conflict (X1) on Employee Performance (Y)

Hypothesis testing shows that work-family conflict significantly impacts Employee Performance, as indicated by a t-statistic value of $4.368 > t\text{-table } 1.65$ and the p-value is $0.000 < 0.05$. Furthermore, the path coefficient value is -0.371 (negative), which means that the work-family conflict variable influences employee performance in the opposite direction or is inversely proportional. The higher the work-family conflict occurs, the more it can affect the decline in employee performance levels and vice versa. Therefore, it can be concluded that work-family conflict (X1) has a significant effect on employee performance (Y).

3. Effect of Work-Life Balance (X1) on Job Satisfaction

Hypothesis testing shows that the Work-life balance variable has a significant effect on Job Satisfaction with a t-statistic value of $2.949 > t\text{-table } 1.65$, and the p-value is $0.003 < 0.05$. Furthermore, the path coefficient value is 0.309 (positive), which means that the influence of the Work-life balance variable on Job Satisfaction is in the same direction or directly proportional. The higher Job Satisfaction, the more significant the impact on employee performance levels. Therefore, it can be concluded that Work-life balance (X2) has a significant effect on Job Satisfaction (Z).

4. Effect of Work-Life Balance (X2) on Employee Performance (Y)

Hypothesis testing shows that the work-life balance variable significantly effect employee performance, as indicated by the t-statistic value of $2.154 > t\text{-table } 1.65$, and the p-value is $0.032 < 0.05$. Furthermore, the path coefficient value is 0.224 (positive), which means that the work-life balance variable influences employee performance directly or proportionally. The higher the work-life balance, the more significant the impact on employee performance levels. Hence, work-life balance (X2) significantly affects employee performance (Y).

5. Effect of Job Satisfaction (Z) on Employee Performance (Y)

Hypothesis testing shows that the Job Satisfaction variable has a significant effect on Employee Performance with a t-statistic value of $4.839 > t\text{-table } 1.65$, and the p-value is $0.000 < 0.05$. Furthermore, the path coefficient value is 0.387 (positive), which means that the influence of the Job Satisfaction variable on Employee Performance is in the same direction or directly proportional. As job satisfaction increases, its influence on employee performance grows stronger. In other words, Job Satisfaction (Z) significantly effect on employee performance (Y).

6. Effect of Work-Family Conflict (X1) on Employee Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (Z)

Hypothesis testing shows that the work-family conflict variable significantly impacts employee performance through Job Satisfaction with a t-statistic value of $3.576 > t\text{-table } 1.65$, and the p-value is $0.000 < 0.05$. Furthermore, the path coefficient value is -0.216 (negative), which means that the influence of the work-family

conflict variable on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction is in the opposite direction or inversely proportional. The higher the work-family conflict, the lower the level of job satisfaction, which can further reduce employee performance. Therefore, it can be concluded that work-family conflict (X1) has a significant effect on Employee Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (Z). Furthermore, based on the calculated value, the indirect influence caused by Job Satisfaction as a mediating variable between work-family conflict and Employee Performance is not greater than the direct influence.

7. Effect of Work-Life Balance (X2) on Employee Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (Z)

The t-statistic value of 2.552 > t-table 1.65 and p-value of 0.011 < 0.05 indicate that work-life balance has a significant influence on employee performance through job satisfaction, in accordance with hypothesis testing. Furthermore, the path coefficient value is 0.120 (positive). This shows that the effect of work-life balance variables on employee performance, through job satisfaction is unidirectional or directly proportional. The higher the work-life balance, the greater the effect on increasing job satisfaction and the impact on improving employee performance. Therefore, work-life balance (X2) has a significant effect on Employee Performance (Y) through Job Satisfaction (Z). The Bootstrapping model can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Bootstrapping model

Information:

X1 = Work-family conflict

X2 = Work-life balance

Z = Job satisfaction

Y = Job employee

DISCUSSION

The effect of work-life balance on employee performance and job satisfaction is examined in this study. The results show a significant relationship between employee performance, job satisfaction, and work-life balance. The results of **hypothesis-1** test provide evidence for the concept that job satisfaction is negatively impacted by work-family conflict. Furthermore, the findings of this study indicate that work-family conflict is a significant predictor of job satisfaction. Many studies report that work-family conflict and job satisfaction are negatively related. As discussed earlier, a reduction in work-family conflict will increase job satisfaction. Work-family conflict has a significant and negative influence on job satisfaction (Zhao et al., 2023). Adverse consequences

such as depression, job burnout, employee turnover, job dissatisfaction, and marital dissatisfaction have been found to increase as a result of excessive work-family conflict (Yadav & Sharma, 2023).

The findings of **hypothesis-2** align with prior research indicating that work-family conflict has negative impacts on employee performance. This includes experiencing job dissatisfaction, emotional exhaustion, depression, and psychological stress. When individuals experience conflicts between their responsibilities as employees and their family roles, they may seek to adjust their work habits to better align with their capabilities. Individuals who want to achieve sustained competitive advantage must be able to balance the allocation of time and energy between their roles as employees and as family members. If there is an imbalance in carrying out these two roles, it will reduce job satisfaction and hinder performance improvement (Zhang et al., 2020). Work-family conflict was found to be negatively related to employee performance in the world of work (Tran et al., 2023).

A work-family conflict is a form of overlapping role conflict, where the pressures from roles in the work and family domains conflict with each other in several ways. Participation in work (family) roles makes family participation (work) roles difficult. Work-family conflict is a conflict related to roles, responsibilities, needs, expectations, duties, and commitments. Several experts who study Work-family conflict use various terms to explain the phenomenon of Work-family conflict (Netemeyer et al., 1996). There are three aspects to work-family conflict: Time-based conflict, strain-based conflict, and behavior-based conflict (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985).

Based on conditions in the company, employees are employed in 3 shifts alternately from morning to evening, and overtime is applied to all production department employees, both male and female employees. Even though overtime work has been implemented, including during holidays, the annual production target has never been achieved. Scholars contend that high overtime rates, the shift work schedule, and excessive time spent at work have all contributed to conflict at work (Work Related Sources of Conflict). Apart from that, if we look at time-based conflict, it can be explained that time spent on activities in one role cannot be devoted to another role. In this context, it is described that there are two types of time-based conflicts. (1) Time pressures from one role prevent a person from meeting expectations in another role, and (2) these pressures make it challenging to focus on one role while physically attending to the responsibilities of another.

Work-family conflict not only happens to female employees but can also affect male employees (Obrenovic et al., 2020). Although traditionally, work-family conflict is often associated with women due to their traditional roles in childcare and household responsibilities; research has shown that male employees can also experience conflict between work and personal life. Some studies show that male employees can also feel the pressure between increased work demands and their family responsibilities or personal lives (Boettcher et al., 2019). For example, rising expectations to be more present at work or involved in time-consuming projects can reduce the time and energy available for family and individual activities. Therefore, it is essential to realize that work-family conflict can affect employees from various backgrounds and genders, and inclusive management strategies need to be developed to help all employees overcome these challenges.

The results of **hypothesis-3** test explain that job satisfaction is significantly influenced by work-life balance. The study's findings corroborate the assertions of professionals that a healthy work-family balance boosts job satisfaction. The feeling of fulfilling both family and employee roles gives employees strength and self-confidence and leads to positive emotional reactions regarding their employees (Qiu & Dauth, 2022). There is a significant influence on work-life balance and job satisfaction, which means that the higher an employee achieves work balance, the more job satisfaction will increase (Fiernaningsih et al., 2019). Work-life balance is positively

related to job satisfaction (Thi et al., 2022). Experts in the fields of sociology and psychology argue that work-life balance is positively correlated with job satisfaction (Uresha, 2020).

Based on **hypothesis-4** testing, the research findings explain that work-life balance has a significant influence on employee performance. The results of this study support earlier research showing that work-life balance is critical to improving employee performance. Understanding how work-life balance influences employee performance is crucial for ensuring the sustainability of the organization (Preena & Preena, 2021). Ignoring the importance of work-life balance within organizations can lead to reduced productivity and performance among employees. When employees have a healthy balance between their work and personal lives, they tend to feel appreciative towards their leaders and the organization as a whole. This sense of gratitude often motivates them to put forth their best efforts in their roles, ultimately leading to enhanced performance (Susanto et al., 2022).

According to the **hypothesis-5** test, job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance. The findings align with prior research indicating that high job satisfaction has multiple positive effects on employees. Satisfied employees tend to actively foster better relationships with their colleagues, promoting teamwork and collaboration. Job satisfaction reduces mental pressure associated with work, enhancing overall well-being and contributing positively to employee performance (Fleury & Grenier, 2018). Job satisfaction will affect employee performance. There is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance because employees who are satisfied and can enjoy their work will tend to perform better in carrying out their roles based on social exchange theory (Cho et al., 2023). The higher the job satisfaction, the higher the work performance. Job satisfaction can predict employee performance positively. Increasing employee job satisfaction affects employee performance (Berhanu, 2023; Lu et al., 2023; Maheshwari, 2022). Studies indicate that satisfied employees contribute positively to their employers by being more productive. When employees are satisfied with their work, they find greater meaning in their tasks and demonstrate confidence in their abilities. Understanding the impact of their role on others also enhances their performance, as they feel competent in completing job-related responsibilities. This confidence in themselves and their colleagues fosters improved employee performance (Memon et al., 2023).

Results of testing the **hypothesis-6**, that there is a mediator between work-family conflict (WFC) and employee performance in the form of job satisfaction. As a mediating variable between work-family conflict and employee performance, job satisfaction has an indirect effect that is not greater than the direct effect (Orellana et al., 2023). This shows that despite the mediating effect through job satisfaction, work-family conflict still has a significant direct effect on employee performance (Ribeiro et al., 2023). Thus, the results of the analysis show that Work-family conflict plays an important role both directly and indirectly in influencing employee performance. It is imperative for management to prioritize addressing work-family conflict, as this can increase job satisfaction and, consequently, improve employee performance. However, it is also important to address work-family conflict directly as its direct impact on Employee Performance remains significant.

The results of testing the seventh hypothesis explain that work-life balance and employee performance are mediated by job satisfaction. As a mediating variable between work-life balance and employee performance, job satisfaction has a smaller indirect impact than the direct impact. This indicates that work-life balance has a smaller indirect impact on employee performance through job satisfaction than the direct impact (Inegbedion, 2024). Furthermore, it appears that work-life balance has a stronger direct influence on employee performance than the indirect influence through job satisfaction as a mediator. Management should prioritize creating a work environment that supports work-life balance to improve employee performance. This includes implementing

policies that support work flexibility, effective time management, and accommodating employees' needs to maintain a healthy balance between work and personal life (Kossek et al., 2022).

V. CONCLUSION

Work-family conflict significantly influences the employee's job satisfaction and performance negatively. The job satisfaction decreases because of this conflict, which in turn reduces the performance. It is also enhanced by several negative outcomes, including emotional exhaustion, psychological stress, and imbalance of role between work and family. It is also discovered that this type of conflict influences male and female employees. Work-life balance has positive implications on employee performance and job satisfaction. A balance between work life and personal life keeps employees more satisfied and better performers. This would imply the relevance of work-life balance policies in enhancing the productivity and performance level of employees. This means that job satisfaction is an important mediator in the relationship of work-family conflict and work-life balance with employee performance. However, its mediation effect is smaller for both relationships compared to the direct effect of each variable, which would indicate that it does not fully buffer the impact of work-to-family conflict on employee performance. In general, this would help to emphasize the importance of addressing work-family conflict and the development of policies for work-life balance as part of improving job satisfaction and increasing employee performance. Management would have to take on strategies that minimize role conflict and support work-life balance in order to achieve the finest employee performance.

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